

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL AWARENESS IN PERSON

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Abstract. *Professional self-determination is a multi-stage process that can be approached from different points of view. Professional self-determination is manifested as a decision-making process. In this case, a person forms and optimizes his inclinations and desires based on the needs of the existing social system*

Keywords: *personality, concept, professional, nervous system, ability, value, education, disposition.*

An important factor in the productivity and understanding of a person's professional formation is his finding meaning in his professional work, planning his professional life, making responsible decisions about choosing a profession and a place of work. Of course, these important professional problems appear in front of a person throughout his life. The ability to understand the role of the individual in the professional context, the relationship to the team and to oneself becomes an important component of human life. Sometimes a person moves away from the profession and begins to feel burdened by it, then a feeling of dissatisfaction with his professional position appears. Also, people are forced to change profession (specialty) and workplace sometimes. It can be noted that a person always needs to determine his attitude towards his profession, sometimes to analyze his professional achievements, to accept the decision to choose a profession or to change it, to identify and correct his career, and to solve issues that are characteristic of other professions. In vocational science, all these problems are called professional identification understood. Naturally, such a complex psychological phenomenon cannot have a single correct definition in psychology. The concept of professional formation in a person has been explained in different ways by research psychologists.

According to the concept of A. Maslow, it reflects the desire of a person to improve and manifest himself. In his concept, the concept of "Identification" is recognized as a close term to the concept of "Self-manifestation".

E.A. Klimov analyzed the professional understanding in detail, making it an important aspect of "psychic development, formation of oneself as a full-fledged participant of the professional community of those who do something useful." E.A. Klimov's opinion on professional understanding is valuable. In his opinion, an easy and short-term calculated career choice is actually made based on the formula "moment rush all future life".

Before the ways of development, a certain attitude to various fields of work, an idea about many professions and an assessment of one's capabilities, an idea about "backup options" of choosing a profession, correct behavior in the socio-economic situation, and many other things characteristic of the internal preparation of the next professional awareness are formed.

E.A. Klimov's opinion can be emphasized from a logical point of view. Professional awareness is not a momentary act of professional choice and does not end with the end of professional training in the chosen specialty, but it continues throughout the entire professional life.

In the psychological and pedagogical literature, 4 groups of factors affecting the process of professional self-determination are distinguished. First of all, it is socio-economic, and it offers young people who are entering the life of society at different stages of development different areas to spend their existing strength and opportunities. First of all, the spectrum of these professions, their change and development prospects are related to the need of society for one or another specialist.

Social and psychological factors make up the second group. First of all, the environment in which a person grew up before and after school education, family, circle of friends, school community and so on.

Under the influence of the social environment, a person's value orientation, his attitude to different groups of professions, specific social expectations and stereotypes are formed.

The third group consists of original psychological factors, which are personal interests and inclinations, general and specific abilities, the level of mental and personal development, memory characteristics, peculiarities of attentional motor skills, and so on.

Finally, the fourth group includes individual psychophysiological characteristics, and the most studied of them is the question of the influence of the main properties of the nervous system on the types of activities. They determine the dynamic characteristics of mental processes, are expressed in the form of different temperaments, and can help to perform a certain type of activity, or, on the contrary, make it difficult.

Another reason that makes it difficult to choose an adequate profession is the low level of psychological knowledge among students, insufficient information about their abilities, individual psychological characteristics and tendencies.

Difficulties in professional self-awareness are also related to not knowing what professional fitness is and how it is formed. There is a widespread misconception that there is a specific purpose for any cocktail.

Lack of self-awareness creates major difficulties in professional self-determination. Some students believe that their expressed interests do not match their aptitudes and aptitudes, while others have difficulty narrowing down the range of careers they can choose for those with many interests and aptitudes. The third have certain professional goals, but do not have the necessary professionally expressed qualities. Most of the students, even their parents, often choose an educational institution or an educational activity instead of paying attention to work. This choice is based on interest in one or another subject. In fact, there is a big difference between academic and cocktail activities within the respective subject.

Prior to the process of professional self-realization, the primary choice of a profession is made at the junior school age, which is characterized by less differentiated ideas about professions. At this stage, very few students think about the possibilities of getting one or another profession, and they think about professions based on external attributes, clothes, behavior, and so on. Since children of this age are developing their personality and psychic properties, they often do not have stable interests and inclinations. It is during this period that students should be introduced to the world of professions and given the opportunity to try themselves in various types of activities, often the interests that arise at this age are the basis for the future professional choice.

The central point of career guidance is to determine the student's interest and inclinations in the types of craft activities. Students with expressed interest and inclinations will have no difficulty in choosing their future profession. It is important for them to have their choice

confirmed by a psychologist. However, many students do not have clear interests and inclinations, or their presence is not related to their professional activities. The main indicator of inclinations is the desire of students to engage in a certain type of activity and school subjects, without forcing them from outside, but according to their inner urge and need. From the above points, it can be seen that in the process of professional self-awareness, personal characteristics are shown as an important aspect of self-awareness assessment of a person.

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